

INVESTMENT FUNDS AS A POSSIBILITY FOR USING ISLAMIC FINANCIAL CONTRACTS IN SERBIA

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Abstract:

The Islamic financial system represents a concept of finance that operates without interest, based on the principles of profit-and-loss sharing and fairness. With global assets exceeding one trillion US dollars, the Islamic financial system is gradually gaining popularity globally, including the Balkans. Currently, the only Islamic bank in the region is Bosnia Bank International. In this paper, we analyze the possibility of applying Islamic financial contracts through investment funds within the existing legal framework in Serbia. Given that the Islamic financial system prohibits interest, investment funds, which rely on profit-and-loss sharing, present a suitable instrument for attracting investors who adhere to Islamic finance principles. The analysis shows that while UCITS funds, which primarily invest in interest-bearing instruments, are not aligned with Islamic principles, Alternative Investment Funds (AIFs) offer greater flexibility. AIFs can invest in real estate, commodities, and shares in business entities, making them suitable for Islamic financial instruments such as musharaka, mudaraba, ijara etc. We conclude that AIFs present a promising opportunity for integrating Islamic finance into Serbia's financial system, attracting ethical investments, and fostering economic growth. Future research should focus on overcoming existing limitations and improving the regulatory environment to enable further development of Islamic finance in Serbia and the Balkans.

Keywords: Islamic financial system, investment funds, Serbia, Alternative Investment Funds (AIFs), Open Investment Funds (OIFs), Undertakings for the Collective Investment in Transferable Securities – UCITS, musharaka, mudaraba, ijara, murabaha, salam, istisna', ethical finance.

INTRODUCTION

Islamic finance is a method of finance that has become a widespread phenomenon since the 1970s. Islamic financial institutions currently manage assets worth over one trillion US dollars. However, Islamic finance is only slowly making its way to the Balkan regions. Currently, the only Islamic bank in the Balkans is Bosnia Bank

International, which was established on October 19, 2000, as the first bank in Europe operating under the principles of Islamic banking. However, there is increasing discussion in Serbia about investments from the United Arab Emirates, where there has been talk of opening the so-called "Royal Bank" from Abu Dhabi (Bećirović, 2014).

Due to the growing interest in Islamic finance, in this paper, we want to analyze the possibility of using Islamic Financial Contracts through investment funds under legal regulatory framework in Serbia. Since Islamic finance does not allow the giving and taking of interest, the financial instruments based on profit and loss sharing, which include investment funds, can be adopted to appeal to the investors following the principles of Islamic finance.

ISLAMIC FINANCIAL INSTRUMENTS

There are two main groups of contracts when it comes to investing in accordance with principles of Islamic finance: partnership contracts and debtor contracts. Partnership contracts largely resemble classical partnerships. In this case, the investor becomes a partner in a new or existing company and shares profits and losses with the other partners.

The first contract is known as "musharaka." Here, the partners invest capital for a specific commercial venture, sharing profits and losses among themselves. Musharaka, generally, is quite similar to classical partnerships and limited partnerships. It is essential to note that the fundamental rule in all partnerships under Islamic law is that a fixed amount of profit, in absolute terms, cannot be stipulated to be paid to the partners, as this would be considered interest.

The second type of partnership is "mudarabah" that also refers to passive partnership. In this case, the investor ("rabb-ul-mal") provides funds, while the money user (entrepreneur, company, etc.) takes on the role of mudarib.

From the perspective of Islamic law, investments in shares are, in general, permitted. The crucial aspect here is to analyze what type of company the money is being invested in. For instance, it is not permissible to invest funds in a company primarily engaged in the production of alcohol, cigarettes or pornography.

Besides shares, there are also so-called "Islamic bonds" or Sukuk. These Islamic bonds are based on classical Islamic debt instruments such as leasing ("ijara"). However, it is important to note that "Islamic bonds" are based on partnership. A partnership among investors arises when a securitization of the contract occurs (Bećirović, 2014).

Deferred payment sales ("bay mu'ajjal") is one of the most important debtor contracts in Islamic finance. This refers to the sale of a commodity, which is not money, on deferred payment terms at the same or a higher price than if the commodity were sold immediately for cash. Since money is not exchanged for money (i.e., there is no

exchange of the same type of commodity), the increase in price does not fall under interest according to Islamic law.

In practice, deferred payment sales are implemented through “murabaha.” Murabaha is a purchase through an intermediary. In this case, the buyer gives an order to the Islamic bank or financial institution to buy a specific product for a certain price, with the buyer promising to buy back the goods. It is crucial that no contract is made between the parties. When the Islamic bank purchases the goods, i.e., takes ownership of the goods, the buyer must fulfill their promise. The Islamic bank sells the ordered goods to the buyer at a predetermined price. The buyer can pay for the goods immediately or in installments at a higher Price (Usmani, 2003).

The term “ijara” refers to the leasing of the benefits of property for a certain compensation.¹⁷ In this case, the Islamic bank acquires an item that will be leased to the user. This contract has the greatest similarity to operating leasing, while financial leasing is not allowed in Islam due to its similarity to interest-based loans. Of course, there are minor differences between operating leasing and ijara, such as the fact that all obligations arising from ownership are borne by the lessor (for example: tax payments, insurance, maintenance of the property), while obligations arising from the use are paid by the lessee, for example: routine expenses, such as energy bills or fuel (Zuhayli, 2003).

“Bay salam” means advance payment for a commodity that will be delivered in the future according to the agreed description. This means that at the conclusion of the contract, the subject of the contract does not yet exist. An example of “bay salam” is when a farmer sells a certain amount of wheat for cash one year in advance. In this case, the Islamic bank (as the buyer of the commodity) must pay the agreed price in advance, and the goods will be delivered after one year. Thus, the Islamic bank will ultimately obtain the physical item at the end of the contract.

Istisna' represents a second type of sale, where goods are traded before they are produced. In the case of istisna', the client orders the manufacturer to produce certain goods in a specific form, and the manufacturer is obligated to organize the necessary labor and materials. The main difference between istisna' and salam is that the subject of istisna' is always a specific product that cannot be found on the market, while bay salam can generally be concluded for any goods. Another difference is that with istisna', the price does not have to be fully paid in advance. Additionally, a salam contract cannot be unilaterally terminated, whereas this is possible with istisna' before work begins. Furthermore, the delivery time does not have to be precisely determined in istisna' (Usmani, 2003). From a practical perspective, istisna' contracts can be used in construction contracts. The Islamic financial institution may undertake the obligation to build, for example, a house, while the client begins paying for the house before the construction is completed and continues the payment after the completion of the construction.

There is also a non-interest-bearing loan. Here, the financial institution gives another person or entity a certain amount of money, which the user must return in the same amount, without subtraction or addition, after a certain period. This contract can be

used by the Islamic bank, for instance, when a client temporarily overdraws the available amount in their current account.

Investment funds in Serbia

Investment funds are institutions for collective investment in which financial resources are gathered. The collected financial resources of the fund are invested in various types of assets, in accordance with the regulations governing investment funds, as well as the investment objectives stated in the operating rules and prospectus, when there is an obligation for its publication, to achieve profits and reduce investment risks.

The assets of the investment fund are owned by the members of the investment fund, proportionate to their participation in the fund, and are separate from the company managing that fund. The operations of investment funds in Serbia are regulated by the Law on Open Investment Funds with Public Offering and the Law on Alternative Investment Funds, while the oversight of the operations of management companies is conducted by the Securities Commission (Securities Commission, Serbia, 2024).

Under Serbian law,¹⁸ investment funds are categorized into two main groups: Open Investment Funds (OIFs) and An Alternative Investment Funds (AIFs).

Open Investment Funds

An Open Investment Fund with Public Offering, also called Undertakings for the Collective Investment in Transferable Securities or UCITS fund, aims for the collective investment of assets collected through the public offering of investment units in the fund, primarily in transferable securities or other liquid financial assets. It operates according to the principle of diversification of investment risk, and its investment units can be redeemed, either directly or indirectly, from the assets of the open investment fund at the request of the unit holders. The Open Investment Funds with Public Offering are accessible to the investment public and are directed at small investors who do not meet the criteria for professional clients under capital market regulations. Therefore, UCITS funds are subject to more numerous restrictions than alternative investment funds.

There are five types of UCITS Funds, depending on the investment goal:

UCITS Preservation Fund: This fund invests in short-term debt securities and cash deposits, aiming to preserve the value of investments and protect against inflation. As the name suggests, these funds strive for capital preservation, making them the lowest

¹⁸ [Law on Open-Ended Investment Funds with Public Offerings](#) ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia," No. 73/2019 and 94/2024) and [Law on Alternative Investment Funds](#) ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia," No. 73/2019 and 94/2024)

risk funds. While investing in these funds won't yield high returns, investors can be assured of the value of their investments remaining stable. The returns of such funds are usually slightly higher than inflation and bank deposit interest rates.

Income UCITS Fund: This fund invests in debt securities. Although the value of the investment may increase, the main goal of these funds is to provide regular income to their members. Consequently, conservative investors, seniors who need supplemental income for their pensions, and those looking to lower portfolio risk typically invest in these funds. These funds generate income that is higher than what preservation funds achieve, accompanied by a greater level of risk. The riskiness of these funds can vary dramatically based on the issuer of the securities they invest in. Additionally, these funds are exposed to interest rate risk — when interest rates rise, the value of income funds decreases.

Growth UCITS Fund: This fund invests in equity securities, aiming to provide high returns over the medium to long term. Such funds invest the largest portion of their assets in stocks, making them riskier than the preceding funds. However, the risk level may vary greatly depending on the specific characteristics of the businesses they invest in and the investment strategies employed. Younger individuals and investors willing to accept significant investment risks primarily invest in these funds.

Balanced UCITS Fund: This fund invests in both equity and debt securities. Its goal is to provide a blend of security, income, and growth for the invested assets. These funds are suitable for investors interested in moderate growth of their investments with moderate risk.

General Purpose UCITS Fund: This fund is a novelty in Serbian legislation and can invest in all asset types in accordance with the limitations set by the Law on Open Investment Funds. Consequently, its riskiness depends on the ultimate decision regarding which types of assets it will invest in.

Alternative Investment Funds

An Alternative Investment Fund (AIF) collects funds from investors with the intention of investing them according to a defined investment policy for the benefit of those investors, and it does not require operational licensing under the laws governing the organization and operation of open investment funds with public offerings. The Law on Alternative Investment Funds is primarily aimed at professional and semi-professional investors, given that the investment policies of AIFs allow for greater investment freedom, which may involve higher concentration of investments in specific companies or issuers, providing financial support to the invested company, and influencing the management of the company being invested in, among other things.

Alternative Investment Funds (AIFs) raise money through public or private offerings and can be established or organized as open-ended or closed-ended, depending on

whether there is a right to redeem investment units or shares from the fund's assets at the request of the fund's members. If money is raised through a public offering, shares are offered to professional, semi-professional, and retail investors, while private offerings are limited to professional and semi-professional investors who have sufficient knowledge and understand the risks involved in investing in such funds.

The Law¹⁹ defines several types of privately offered AIFs, with the classification criterion being the type of assets invested in (e.g., private equity AIF, venture capital AIF, privately offered real estate AIF, etc.).

An open-ended AIF represents a separate asset, without legal personality (legal entity), organized and managed by an Alternative Investment Fund Management Company (AIFMC) in its own name and on behalf of the AIF's members, in accordance with the law, the fund's rules of operation, and/or its prospectus, if required. Units in an open-ended AIF are redeemed at the request of members, directly or indirectly, from the fund's assets, under the terms and conditions specified in the fund's rules of operation and/or prospectus, if required, and before the liquidation process or termination of the AIF. Open-ended AIFs with public offerings can invest in certain types of assets that UCITS funds are not allowed to invest in, permitting them to take on slightly higher risks.

Types of closed-ended AIFs include:

Closed-ended AIF without legal entity – a separate asset, without legal personality, organized and managed by an AIFMC in its own name and on behalf of the AIF's members, in accordance with the law and the fund's rules of operation. Units in such AIFs cannot be redeemed from the fund's assets at the request of members. A closed-ended AIF without legal personality is always managed by an AIFMC.

Closed-ended AIF with legal entity – a legal entity established as a joint-stock company or limited liability company, founded and managed by an AIFMC in its name and on its behalf, in accordance with the law, the fund's rules of operation, and/or its prospectus, if required, and the AIF's statute. Shares in such AIFs cannot be redeemed from the fund's assets at the request of members. Close-ended AIF with legal entity and intenal management – a close-ended AIF with legal entity that manages its own assests without an AIFMC and simultaneously acts as its own AIFMC.

¹⁹ [Law on Alternative Investment Funds](#) ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia," No. 73/2019 and 94/2024)

Compatibility of Investment Funds in Serbia with principles of Islamic finance

The compatibility of Investment Funds with principles of Islamic finance mainly depend on the type of assets the fund is investing in.

In accordance with the Law, the investment funds can invest in various forms of assets, but there are limitation depending on whether a fund is established as an Open-ended fund with a public offering (UCITS fund) or as an Alternative investment fund (AIF). UCITS funds can invest in transferable securities, money market instruments, units of other UCITS funds, cash deposits, debt securities, securities issued by international financial institutions, and financial derivatives. Most of these assets are interest based and are not permissible in accordance with the principles of Islamic finance.

The assets of Alternative investment funds (AIFs), depending on their type, can be invested in transferable securities, money market instruments, units of UCITS funds, shares in other AIFs, bank deposits, debt securities and loan receivables. Most of these assets are also interest based. However, in addition to these, AIFs can also invest in commodities traded on commodity exchanges, real estate, shares in limited liability companies, and more. The second group of investments can be in line with both Law in Serbia and principles of Islamic finance.

Taking this into account, Alternative investment funds can enable the use of Islamic partnership instruments for investing, i.e., investments in shares and other business entities. Additionally, from the perspective of mobilization, investment funds are similar to the "mudaraba" contract, making them a good opportunity for mobilizing and investing money in accordance with the principles of Islamic finance. Islamic debt contracts through alternative investment funds can invest in business entities engaged in operational leasing, deferred payment sales, as well as salam/istisna' transactions. It is important to emphasize here that the restriction on investing the assets of a closed-end investment fund does not apply to investments in business entities (general partnerships, limited liability companies, limited partnerships, and closed joint-stock companies).

CONCLUSION

Under the current regulations governing investment funds in Serbia, a number of original Islamic financial instruments can be utilized. The laws on Investment Funds allow for capital accumulation in a manner similar to the theoretical framework of Islamic finance.

This is especially true for Alternative Investment Funds (AIFs) that present a promising avenue for integrating Islamic financial principles into Serbia's financial system. By leveraging the flexibility of AIFs and structuring them to align with principles of Islamic finance, Serbia can attract investments from a wider investor community, especially from the Middle East, and expand its financial ecosystem. This integration not only aligns with global trends in ethical and sustainable finance but

also opens new opportunities for economic growth and diversification in the region. Future research and policy development should focus on addressing the limitations and creating a more conducive environment for Islamic finance to succeed in Serbia and the broader Balkan region.

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